

Approximate solution of the new gravitational field equation

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Abstract

Based on the numerical solution of the new gravitational field equation, an approximate component of the metric of the gravitational field of a point mass is obtained. Unlike the solution to the Einstein equation, this solution does not contain singularities.

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1. Introduction

Einstein introduced Riemannian space into physics as a physical object. This made it possible to consistently describe gravity and its accompanying phenomena, at least in the region of not too large fields.

The presented material does not go beyond the principles of the general theory of relativity; on the contrary, the theory managed to include a full-fledged principle of conservation of energy, which is absent in Einstein's theory of gravity.

The first results were obtained in works [1-3]. The energy-momentum tensor of the gravitational field has been found²

$$f_{\mu}^{\nu} = -\frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \left(\frac{D \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} \right) = -\frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\nu}} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\beta} \right).$$

Following Einstein's recipe [4], this quantity is introduced into the Einstein equation. Since this quantity is identical to part of the Ricci tensor, Einstein's equation is shortened

$$-\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} - \frac{1}{2} \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} R = \kappa T_{\mu}^{\nu}. \quad (1)$$

This is a new covariant equation of the gravitational field that satisfies the law of conservation of energy.

1.1 The Schwarzschild problem

The Schwarzschild problem (search for the field of a point source) is solved in the same way as the Einstein equation.

Looking for solutions in the form

$$ds^2 = s(r)dt^2 - p(r)dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2.$$

Solving the equation for empty space

$$\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\alpha}}{\partial x^{\alpha}} - \Gamma_{\mu\beta}^{\alpha} \Gamma_{\nu\alpha}^{\beta} = 0. \quad (2)$$

From this equation find the components of the mixed tensor, up to a non-zero factor, are equal:

$$\frac{s''}{s'} - \frac{p'}{p} - \frac{s'}{s} = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{p''}{2p} - \frac{p'p'}{2p^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} - \frac{s's'}{4s^2} = 0, \quad (4)$$

where the prime denotes the derivative with respect to r . Equate these components to zero and obtain a system of ordinary differential equations. Excluding the value p'/p from which obtain a third-order equation [3]:

$$\left(\frac{s''}{s'} \right)' - \left(\frac{s'}{s} \right)' - \frac{s's'}{2s^2} = \frac{4}{r^2}. \quad (5)$$

Unable to find an analytical solution to this equation.

Figure 1: Dependence of g_{00} on the ratio r/r_g . Schwarzschild solutions of the Einstein equation (dotted line) and a numerical solution of the exact gravitational field equation (2) (solid line).

Source: Author.

² It was shown in [3] that this tensor in the Newtonian limit is asymptotically equal to the field energy density.

When solving the equation numerically, asymptotic proximity to the Schwarzschild solution was used. This made it possible to use the Schwarzschild solution values $1-1/r$ as boundary conditions close to the expected solution. As expected, in the region of relatively small values the solution follows the Schwarzschild solution. Then, similarly to the Schwarzschild solution, it quickly decreases (Fig. 1). But the difference from the Schwarzschild solution, the solution to equation (9) remains positive, although extremely small. A potential well is observed with an almost limiting potential value, which is equal to $\varphi = -c^2$. The width of the potential well of the solution is noticeably larger than the Schwarzschild radius $r_g = 1$ Figure (2). There are no features or abnormalities in the surrounding area on the monotonic dependence of the solution. Moreover, there is no indication that the expected singularity is present at the origin, similar to the singularity formed by a point source in well-known classical problems on the monotonic dependence of the solution. Moreover, there is no indication that the expected singularity is present at the origin, similar to the singularity formed by a point source in well-known classical problems.

Figure 2: The Figure (1), stretched 5000 times, the horizontal section of the solution to equation (9) has a positive value, but so small that it graphically merges with the coordinate axis.

Source: Author.

The picture becomes quite simple if plot the value of $\ln g_{00}$ see Figure (3).

The metric component in the region of large values is well approximated by the expression

$$g_{00} \approx \exp\left(-\frac{630}{r^3} r_g\right) \quad (6)$$

This expression is asymptotically true in the region of small $\frac{r}{r_g}$. You can use an additional condition for large $\frac{r}{r_g}$

$$g_{00} \approx 1 - \frac{r_g}{r} \approx \exp\left(-\frac{r_g}{r}\right). \quad (7)$$

Conditions (6) and (7) are simultaneously asymptotically equal (each in its own region) to the expression

$$g_{00} \approx \exp\left(-\frac{r_g}{r} - \frac{630}{r^3} r_g\right). \quad (8)$$

This expression can be used to estimate the Newtonian potential of a point source of the exact gravitational field equation [3]. Thus, the problem of singularity finds its solution within the framework of general relativity. From expression (8) and equation (4) one can find

$$g_{rr} \approx \left(\frac{r_g}{r^2} + \frac{1890}{r^4} r_g\right),$$

asymptotically equal to the Schwarzschild solution.

Figure 3: Dependence of $\ln(g_{00})$ on the ratio $\frac{r}{r_g}$.

Source: Author.

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